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Rangelands Vegetation under Different Management Systems and Growth Stages in North Darfur State, Sudan, (*Range components*)

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Research Article

Rangelands Vegetation under different Management Systems and Growth Stages in North Darfur State, Sudan (*Range components*)

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted at Um Kaddada locality, North Darfur State, at two sites (closed and open) for two consecutive periods, 2008 and 2009 during flowering and seed setting stages. The main objective of the study was to evaluate rangelands at the locality under closed and open management systems at different growth stages.

Specific objectives are to determine the effects of range management systems and growth stages on range components. A split plot design was used to study range composition (Live plants, litter, bare soil and fecal dropping). The results showed highly significant ($P < 0.01$) differences in range component effect (plant, litter, bare soil and fecal droppings) between closed and open areas, but fecal droppings were not significantly ($P > 0.05$) different during growth stages. Closed areas had higher live plants compared with open rangelands.

The study concluded that the closed rangelands are better than open rangelands, and both of the two ecological zones were deteriorated in both quality and quantity, so, the study suggested that improvement and rehabilitation of such lands rangelands should be done.

Further research work is needed to assess range components across different ecological zones in North Darfur State.

ABSTRACT IN ARABIC

ملخص الدراسة

أجريت هذه الدراسة في موقعين (منطقة محجوزة وأخرى مفتوحة) لموسمين متتاليين 2008 و 2009 خلال مرحلتى الإزهار وتكوين البذور. الهدف الرئيسي من هذه الدراسة هو تقييم المراعى بالمنطقة، تم استخدام تصميم القطاعات المنفصلة لدراسة مكونات المرعى. تمت دراسة عوامل نظم الإدارة (مناطق محجوزة ومفتوحة) ومراحل النمو (مرحلتى الإزهار وتكوين البذور) لمعرفة أثرها على المراعى الطبيعية. تم حصر وتحديد النباتات الحية، بقايا النباتات، الأرض الجرداء ومخلفات الحيوانات بالمنطقة. أوضحت الدراسة وجود فروقات معنوية عالية ($P < 0.01$) فى مكونات المرعى (النباتات الحية، بقايا النباتات، الأراضى الجرداء ومخلفات الحيوانات) بين المناطق المحجوزة والمفتوحة، لكن لا توجد فروقات معنوية ($P > 0.05$) فى مخلفات الحيوانات أثناء مراحل النمو. كانت نسبة النباتات الحية أعلى فى المناطق المحجوزة بالمقارنة مع المناطق المفتوحة. هنالك حاجة لمزيد من البحوث لتقييم مكونات المراعى الطبيعية فى الأحزمة البيئية المختلفة فى ولاية شمال دارفور.

Keywords: Growth stage, Management, Live plant, Litter, Bare soil, Fecal dropping.

INTRODUCTION

Study area

The study area is part of what is called sedentary zone, located between zones of camel owning nomads to the north and cattle owners nomads to the south. The area is dominantly inhabited by Barti tribes who are accustomed to a sedentary way of life and are more attached to their land than other tribes to the north and south.

Different systems of climatic classification designated Um Kaddada as arid; Yousif (2005) designates the area as part of the Sudan arid zone, Annual precipitation is ranging between 100 – 170mm.

Since 1980, there have been only four occasions where the rainfall has exceeded 200mm at Um Kaddada locality. That was in 1986, 1992, 1994 and 2000 respectively. In almost all other years during this period until 2009, total annual rainfall has been below 160 mm (Table 1).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted at Um Kaddada locality, North Darfur State, Sudan. Um- Kaddada locality is located in the eastern part of North Darfur State of the western Sudan (167 km from Al Fashir - Capital of North Darfur State) (Figure 1), between longitudes 26° - 27° E, and latitudes 13° - 14° N, covering an area of about 15000 km², (Ministry of Agriculture, Animal Resources and Irrigation, 2006).

The study was carried out during the rainy season (Flowering stage) and the end of rainy season (Seed setting) (late August and late October) for two consecutive years (2008 and 2009). The samples were taken from two sites (open and closed) at Eastern part of Um Kaddada town. Two points were chosen at in each site. Within each point, eight transects 100m long were taken in a radiating manner (Point size: 200x200m).

The measurement tools consisted of measuring tape (100 meter), loop (3/4 diameter) and recording sheet. Information used in the attainment of this study included both primary and secondary data. Primary data were vegetation measurements collected from closed and open rangelands, sources of secondary data were published and unpublished reports and studies covering variety of related topic to the study area.

Variables measurement

Four variables were measured. These are: the number of live plants, the litter quantity, the area of bare soil and the content of fecal droppings. When the skinned process had happened, they were transformed in percentage.

Statistical analysis

Data were arranged in split-plot design, taking ecological zone as main plot and the period as sub-plot (Steel and Torrie, 1980), growth stage was also taken as a factor and considered as a sub-sub plot. The data was first analyzed for each period separately then combined for the two periods. SPSS software program was used for statistical analyses.

RESULTS

The effects of management and growth stage on range components during the first period (2008) are shown in Tables (2). Management x growth stage interaction effects on %plant, %litter and % bare soil were significant ($P < 0.01$). Closed area during seed setting had the highest %plant while the open area during seed setting had the lowest % Bplant. Litter and bare soil on open area during seed setting had highest percentage while closed area during seed setting and open area during flowering stage had lowest percentage respectively.

Management x growth stage interaction had no effect ($P > 0.05$) on fecal droppings (Table 2).

Management expressed the main significant ($P < 0.01$) effects on %plant, %litter accumulation, %bare soil and %fecal droppings. Closed area revealed the highest live plant whereas the open one had the highest litter, bare soil and fecal droppings (Table 2).

Growth stage significantly ($P < 0.01$) affected % plant, %litter and %bare soil. The highest plants percentage was during the flowering stage whereas the highest litter and bare soils were observed during the seed setting stage. However, no significant effect ($P > 0.05$) of growth stage on fecal droppings, but flowering stage had the highest percentage of fecal droppings (Table 2).

Table (3) shows the effects of management and growth stage on range components during the second season (2009). Management had significant ($P < 0.01$) effects on %plant, %litter, %bare soil and % fecal droppings. Closed area had the highest plant while open rangelands had the highest litter, bare soil and fecal droppings.

Growth stage had significant ($P < 0.01$) effect on %litter and ($P < 0.05$) on %plant. Flowering stage had the highest plant while seed setting had the highest litter. No significant ($P > 0.05$) effect of growth stage on bare soil and fecal droppings were found. Seed setting stage had the highest percentage of bare soil whereas, flowering stage had the highest fecal droppings (Table 3). No significant ($P > 0.05$) interaction effects of management x growth stage on range components were found (Table 3).

The combined analysis:

Table (4) shows the results of the combined analysis of range components for the two seasons (2008 and 2009).

The season had the main significant ($P < 0.05$) effects on %litter. Period 2009 had higher litter than season 2008. However, no significant main effects ($P > 0.05$) of period on range components were found (Table 4).

Management significantly ($P < 0.01$) affected %plant, %litter, %bare soil and %fecal droppings. Closed area had the highest live plant while open rangelands had the highest litter, bare soil and fecal droppings (Table 4).

Growth stage had the main significant ($P < 0.01$) effects on live plant, litter and bare soil. Range component had highest live plant during flowering stage, whereas litter and bare soil were found highest during seed setting. No main effect ($P > 0.05$) of growth stage on fecal droppings (Table 4).

Year x management interaction had no effect ($P > 0.05$) on range component. However, year x growth stage interaction had significant ($P < 0.01$) effect on live plant and bare soil, but no significant effect ($P > 0.05$) on litter and fecal droppings (Table 4).

Management x growth stage and Year x management x growth stage linteractions had significant ($P < 0.01$) effects on live plant, litter and bare soil, but no significant ($P > 0.05$) effect on fecal droppings were found (Table 4).

DISCUSSION

Range component was affected by management and growth stage (Tables 2 and 3). These effects were consistent during both periods (2008 and 2009) (Table 4). Closed areas had highest live plant compared with open rangelands (Tables 2, 3 and 4). This difference may be partially attributed to protection by the guards and hedges. Also severe grazing pressures in open areas affect the range component which was reflected in reduced desirable species and high percentages of bare soil and animal faeces. Thomas *et al.* (1988) stated that grazing pressure influences herbaceous composition.

Flowering stage had higher live plant compared with seed setting stage (Tables 2, 3 and 4). These differences may be attributed to the low rain during September and October.

Figure 1: Location Map of the study area. North Darfur State, Sudan.
Source: UN Cartographic Section, (2004)

Table (1): Rainfall average in Um Kaddada locality (2008 and 2009)

month period	Apr.	May.	Jun.	Jul.	Aug.	Sep.	Tot
2008	3.3	7	-	31.4	18.9	80.9	141.5
2009	-	-	-	38.3	61.8	47	147.1
Average	1.7	3.5	-	34.9	40.4	64	144.3

Source: Um Kaddada Meteorological Station (2009)

Table (2): Effects of management and growth stage on Range Components (season 2008)

Factors		%Plant	%Litter	%Bare soil	%Fecal droppings
Management					
Close		87.75	6.66	5.16	0.44
Open		58.38	14.81	24.88	1.94
SE±		1.72**	1.20**	1.42**	0.26**
Growth Stage					
Flowering		83.97	6.41	8.47	1.22
Seed Setting		62.16	15.06	21.56	1.16
SE±		1.72**	1.20**	1.42**	0.26 ^{ns}
Interaction: Management x Growth Stage					
Close	Flowering	86.38	7.19	5.81	0.63
	Seed Setting	89.13	6.13	4.50	0.25
Open	Flowering	81.56	5.63	11.13	1.81
	Seed Setting	35.19	24.00	38.63	2.06
SE±		2.43**	1.70**	2.01**	0.37 ^{ns}

^{ns} not significant, * significant at 0.05 level, ** significant at 0.01 level**Table (3):** Effects of management and growth stage on Range Components (season 2009)

Factors		%Plant	%Litter	%Bare soil	%Fecal droppings
Management					
Close		85.16	7.59	7.03	0.22
Open		53.63	19.56	25.50	1.31
SE±		2.30**	1.43**	1.71**	0.19**
Growth Stage					
Flowering		73.22	10.28	15.69	0.81
Seed Setting		65.56	16.88	16.84	0.72
SE±		2.30*	1.43**	1.71 ^{ns}	0.19 ^{ns}
Interaction: Management x Growth Stage					
Close	Flowering	88.31	5.31	6.06	0.31
	Seed Setting	82.00	9.88	8.00	0.13
Open	Flowering	58.13	15.25	25.31	1.31
	Seed Setting	49.13	23.88	25.69	1.31
SE±		3.25 ^{ns}	2.03 ^{ns}	2.41 ^{ns}	0.26 ^{ns}

^{ns} not significant, * significant at 0.05 level, ** significant at 0.01 level

Table (4): Effects of different seasons, management and growth stage on Range components (Combined analysis).

Factors			% Plant	% Litter	% Bare soil	% Fecal droppings
Season						
2008			73.06	10.73	15.02	1.19
2009			69.39	13.58	16.27	0.77
SE ±			1.44 ^{ns}	0.94*	1.11 ^{ns}	0.16 ^{ns}
Management						
Close			86.45	7.13	6.09	0.33
Open			56.00	17.19	25.19	1.63
SE±			1.44**	0.94**	1.11**	0.16**
Growth Stage						
Flower stage			78.59	8.34	12.08	1.02
Seed Stage			63.86	15.97	19.20	0.94
SE±			1.44**	0.94**	1.11**	0.16 ^{ns}
Interaction (SE±):						
Season x Management			2.03 ^{ns}	1.32 ^{ns}	1.57 ^{ns}	0.23 ^{ns}
Season x Growth Stage			2.03**	1.32 ^{ns}	1.57**	0.23 ^{ns}
Management x Growth Stage			2.03**	1.32**	1.57**	0.23 ^{ns}
Interaction: Season x Management x Growth Stage						
2008	Close	Flowering	86.38	7.19	5.81	0.63
		Seed Setting	89.13	6.13	4.50	0.25
	Open	Flowering	81.56	5.63	11.13	1.81
		Seed Setting	35.19	24.00	38.63	2.06
2009	Close	Flowering	88.31	5.31	6.06	0.31
		Seed Setting	82.00	9.88	8.00	0.13
	Open	Flowering	58.13	15.25	25.31	1.31
		Seed Setting	49.13	23.88	25.69	1.31
SE±			2.87**	1.87**	2.22**	0.32 ^{ns}

^{ns} not significant, * significant at 0.05 level, ** significant at 0.01 level

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